

**FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP****Mukhsiddinov Mansurjon Makhmudjon ugli**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18845304>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 26th February 2026Accepted: 27th Februar 2026Online: 28th February 2026**KEYWORDS***Social entrepreneurship, social enterprise, social innovation, sustainable development, social innovation***ABSTRACT**

This article analyses foreign experience in developing social entrepreneurship, particularly the British model. The study highlights the legislative consolidation of the concept of social entrepreneurship, the introduction of the Community Interest Company (CIC) legal form, the asset protection mechanism, and the state's institutional and financial support system..

In recent years, social entrepreneurship has emerged in many countries around the world as an effective mechanism for addressing social problems. Foreign experience shows that a favourable legal environment created by the state, financial support mechanisms and institutional infrastructure play a crucial role in the sustainable development of social entrepreneurship.

Social enterprise in the UK has developed since the late 20th century, and there are now around 70,000 enterprises, employing over 2 million people and contributing £24 billion to the economy. The sector is growing through government support, special funds and incubators.

The UK experience

The UK is one of the leading countries in the development of social enterprise. In this country:

- The concept of "Social Enterprise" is enshrined in law;
- A special legal form – the Community Interest Company (CIC) – has been introduced;
- Government grants and social investment funds operate;
- A social impact assessment system is developed.

As a result, social enterprises are actively involved in the healthcare, education, environmental and employment sectors. In the UK, incubators and accelerators are actively working to develop social entrepreneurship, providing support from the idea stage through to investment-ready projects. The £10 million Social Incubator Fund supports new start-ups through 10 incubators, while the Big Potential programme helps prepare them for investment of up to £500,000. Social enterprise classes are taught in schools and universities; for example, the Social Enterprise Academy has delivered projects in over 500 schools.

The existence of a legal framework is a crucial factor in the sustainable development of social entrepreneurship. In foreign practice, particularly in the United Kingdom, the concept of social entrepreneurship is firmly established not only in theory but also at a legislative level.

This country is one of the first to introduce institutional mechanisms for the development of social entrepreneurship.

In the UK, the concept of “social enterprise” is recognised as an official economic entity. A social enterprise is an organisation that generates income through commercial activities but directs the majority of its profits towards social objectives. This model reconciles profit-making with the creation of social impact.

The Impact Readiness Fund (2014) was established to promote social investments, teaching social organisations how to attract private sector funding. The organisation ‘Yaxshi Moliya’ manages the social investment market, utilising grants, loans, bonds and crowdfunding. The government provides support through tax incentives and by awarding public contracts to social enterprises.

In 2005, a special legal form – the Community Interest Company (CIC) – was introduced. A CIC sets a social purpose as its primary priority and conducts its activities accordingly. This form differs from a standard commercial enterprise in the following respects:

- limited distribution of profits;
- an asset protection mechanism (‘asset lock’);
- a legally defined social purpose;
- mandatory annual social reporting.

The most important feature of the CIC model is the “asset lock” principle. Under this principle, the company's assets and net profit cannot be fully appropriated for personal benefit by shareholders or founders. A large portion of the profit is directed towards social projects, the community's interests, or the expansion of the organisation's social activities.

This mechanism distinguishes a social enterprise from a conventional business and legally guarantees its social mission.

Conclusion

The experience of the United Kingdom shows that for social entrepreneurship to be developed effectively, its legal status must be clearly defined. A legally enshrined social enterprise model:

- increases investor confidence;
- ensures operational transparency;
- guarantees the primacy of social objectives;
- generates sustainable economic and social outcomes.

This experience is of significant practical importance for countries aiming to develop social entrepreneurship, including Uzbekistan.

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